

SPORTS MEDICINE AND HEALING PHYSICAL EDUCATION

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Abstract. This article is about the current state of sports medicine and physical therapy. The article also mentions the formation of sports medicine in the historical context. You will find a detailed description of the practical application and action of sports medicine and physical therapy in this article.

Keywords: sports, medicine, sports medicine, physical therapy, professional sports, prevention.

Sports medicine is a young and actively developing science that assists coaches and athletes during training. It differs from rural medicine in that sports doctors work with the human body, which is physically overloaded much more and, accordingly, there may be more potential injuries and complications.

For a long time, sports medicine in Russia did not meet the requirements of international standards. It was more like primitive control and formal examinations of athletes. There were no clear recommendations for sports nutrition - special supplements were simply not on sale, professional athletes made do with ordinary products with a standard set of nutrients.

Therapeutic physical culture - independent medical school discipline, which uses physical education to prevent exacerbations and treat many diseases and injuries, as well as restore ability to work. The specificity of therapeutic physical culture is that, in comparison with other methods of treatment, it uses physical exercise as the main therapeutic agent, which is a significant stimulator of the vital functions of the human body.

In the middle of the 20th century, science stopped in its development, as officials were guided by only by their own interests, without listening to the opinions of professionals, without allocating enough funds for high-quality diagnostics of the health of athletes, both amateur and professional. Despite this, the requirements for the results became taller. This explains the increased incidence of injuries, which often deprived people of the ability to even perform simple movements. This was especially true for artistic gymnastics, figure skating, and sports related to acrobatics. It was simply impossible to survive in such a regime. Add to this the great psychological stress associated with increased responsibility.

The formation of sports medicine started only in the 21st century. Scientific research in the field of sports psychology, dietetics, and pharmaceuticals has also not been carried out. All knowledge was accumulated by the coaches themselves and was used spontaneously in relation to athletes, solely based on their own experience. It would be good if this experience happened. Unfortunately, in the history of the development of sports medicine, there are even cases when many former athletes took on the functions of doctors for the rehabilitation and recovery of athletes. Often there was not enough personal experience and no professional knowledge. This ended with promising people leaving the sport for health reasons. This situation had an extremely negative impact on both the state of sports and the state of medicine.

It is believed that the tasks of sports medicine have not yet been defined because it is confused with physical culture. But the loads of ordinary people to maintain general tone and the loads of professional athletes are completely different things.

Sports Medicine is also often confused with physical therapy. For people involved in physical education, the loads are evenly distributed across all muscle groups, classes are dosed, there is no preparation for competitions, there is no responsibility for the result, and therefore there is no psychological stress. Ordinary people do not adhere to a sports regime and do not control their diet. And, most importantly, they decide for themselves when to rest, leave and engage in other leisure activities.

Professional sport is a serious matter. Training takes place, as a rule, twice a day. Half a day is devoted to working in the gym: in any weather, in any condition, in any mood. Therefore, in order to maintain such a schedule, control over training, nutrition, and muscle condition is necessary. Athletes have a lot of free time rarity _ Prevention of various diseases is necessary, especially during competitions. Depending on the sport, the loads always fall on the same muscles. The body, muscles, internal state gets used to a certain algorithm of actions, there is nothing new, everything is always expected.

For professional athletes, the body is a tool for improving the quality and standard of life. This tool should work well and a lot. The sport has become more complex and younger. If in the middle of the 20th century people started doing rhythmic gymnastics at the age of 15-16, now they are looking for trainers for students in kindergartens. That is, children's sports medicine comes first, since at the age of 18-19, gymnasts already leave sports and begin coaching. The peak of training occurs in adolescence, when it is necessary to simultaneously think

about the development of the body and the results in sports. This complicates the task of sports medicine. Also, it should be noted that for athletes, adolescence is a difficult period in terms of sports in that it is necessary to clearly monitor the load in order to avoid deterioration in physical condition and health in the village. Otherwise, athletes can even overload their backs and “develop scoliosis,” where the medical diagnosis will be refusal from sports, and this is even in the best case. Unfortunately, here coaches have a huge responsibility not only for the present, but also for the future of the athletes. And this is just one side of the coin. Adolescence is also a difficult period psychologically. This is a period of crisis; it becomes easier to traumatize a teenager’s psyche than it might seem. Therefore, it is impossible undershot the importance of sports medicine and the work of coaches.

Sports medicine has a number of tasks:

- Assisting the coach in selecting candidates for professional sports;
- Guiding the younger generation through sports activities for many years;
- Determining the optimal work and rest regime is individual for each athlete;
- Recommendations on the type of nutrition during different periods of activity ;
- Prevention of injuries due to increased physical activity;
- Monitoring the intake of pharmaceutical drugs;
- Development of a set of measures to increase performance and improve results ;
- Proper treatment and rehabilitation after sports injuries; control over hygiene and general diseases;
- Doping system in sports.

Sports medicine also studies pathological processes that occur in high-level athletes. As a result unprofessional approach on the part of medical personnel who have no idea about physical activity; there have been many such pathologies in the history of Russian sports, including spontaneous deaths during training. The modern situation, of course, has changed, but such cases still occur.

In order for a sports doctor to apply all his knowledge and experience, he must have the authority to remove a person from competition or training if this threatens injury or disability. A compromise can only be full financial support for athletes, which allows them to recover faster or undergo a course of treatment abroad.

Many medical professionals fought for the implementation of rules in the training and nutrition regime, as well as for the distribution of loads. But their proposals remained unheeded. The sports system is interested in results more than in the health of those who bring these results. This negatively affects athletes, or rather, their health. For trainers, the doctor is often not the first authority.

This is not counting the usual disciplines, which are mandatory for medical doctors. Even rehabilitation after sports injuries has different principles, a different methodology than that of ordinary people.

A sports doctor is, first of all, a specialist in the field of high stress, who must know how the body behaves under extreme conditions. During heavy physical training, the human body loses immunity and minerals in large quantities. Body systems that are genetically weak may fail at the wrong time and prevent participation in competitions:

- 1) Cardiovascular system;
- 2) Digestive tract;
- 3) Kidneys.

Medical staff of national teams must be aware of the health status of each participant. The approach is carried out individually, taking into account the characteristics and degree of training of the athlete.

It is possible that something unexpected might happen during the trip and one of the participants in the competition will get sick. Taking care of your health before competitive competitions falls on the sports doctor. Therefore, he must have knowledge of pharmaceuticals that are approved by the doping committee and do not contain prohibited substances, even if they were used for their intended purpose.

Great importance. In hot countries, where local insects carry infections to which Russian athletes do not have immunity, there is a risk of getting sick and getting sick even before the competition. It is necessary to know what diseases people from other regions of the world are most susceptible to. Vaccinations are given in advance to protect competition participants from infectious diseases.

For example, in India there are a lot of malarial mosquitoes, hepatitis, fever, and dirty water. Dysentery, typhoid fever and cholera are characteristic of eastern countries. You should also observe caution at competitions in Mexico and Brazil. The local climate is favorable for the proliferation of parasites in water. Symptoms may include everyday life poisoning, disorders of the digestive system, and the athlete's incapacitation.

Diagnosis of the athlete's body in sports medicine. In professional athletes, doctors often diagnose an increase in the number of coronary vessels. This is a kind of protective mechanism to provide oxygen to the heart muscle and growing tissues of the body. With a lack of nutrients - building materials for tissues - the body does not have time to grow new blood vessels. As a result, the heart does not receive enough oxygen and the tissues die. This process occurs against the backdrop of intense training. A striking example is the actor bodybuilder Vladimir Turchinsky. In pursuit of muscle mass and athletic achievements, he did not take into account the physiological characteristics of his body, got carried away with the loads, and neglected the regime and nutritious nutrition. With constant filming and stress, the body could not stand it, and the actor died of a heart attack.

Diagnostics using equipment is greatly helped by the athletes themselves describing their sensations and well-being. But often, in pursuit of results, people hide their condition from doctors and, possibly, from themselves. In this mode, injuries most often occur, after which a long period of treatment and rehabilitation begins.

The longest The process is rehabilitation. During this period, heavy loads are contraindicated, because the muscles and tendons are unaccustomed to regular loads and there is a risk of re-injury.

During this period it is shown:

lymphatic massage;

physiotherapeutic procedures ;

moderate loads;

enhanced nutrition;

drinking enough water; - vitamins and mineral complexes.

Rehabilitation professional athletes after injuries. You should not rush to switch to normal loads. The musculoskeletal system is very vulnerable after injury. Experienced trainers in such cases control the loads and keep them at an average level. Based on the results of MRI and X-ray, the sports doctor monitors the condition of the tissues - to what extent they have recovered and are ready for stress.

It is important that the athlete understands that at the stage of restoring the functional capabilities of the body there is no need to rush. As they say, time heals, but you have to wait for it. Of great importance is the help of a psychologist or a sports doctor who can convince a person of the need to wait. For his own good.

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Thus, we see what a big role sports medicine plays. And also, its importance for the development of the country in the sports direction, without numerous injuries, as was the case before.

It is also important that athletes understand that their health does not depend solely on doctors. It is important to monitor your own health, loads, pace, rhythm. During the recovery period, he learns to endure and wait, and not turn a blind eye to his problems and again put their health at risk.

At the same time, in these cases and in preventive situations, it is necessary to pay attention to physical therapy, which is often not taken seriously by athletes. It also helps during the recovery period.

The most important thing is to look after your health and not neglect prevention, diagnosis, treatment and recovery. Health needs to be taken care of regardless of a person's physical fitness.

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